

Study of Prevalence of Depression Anxiety and Alcohol Abuse in Patients Diagnosed with Pulmonary Tuberculosis on Anti-Tubercular Drugs**S Md Shahid Basha¹, P Ramya Keerthi², Inakollu Vamsi Krishna³, S Sarath Krishna⁴, S Md Sajid Basha⁵**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Institute of Mental Health, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, India²Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Institute of Mental Health, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, India³Associate Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Institute of Mental Health, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore, Andhra Pradesh, India⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Government Medical College, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study was conducted to know the incidence of depression, anxiety and alcohol abuse in patients suffering from pulmonary tuberculosis. A cross sectional study was conducted at Tuberculosis and chest diseases Out Patient Department for a period of one year with a sample size of 100 patients who were diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis are on anti-tubercular drugs. The tools used were socio demographic data, Modified Kuppaswamy Classification, the MINI- International Neuro Psychiatric Interview Scale, Hamilton depression rating scale (HAMD), and AUDIT (Alcohol use disorder identification test). Current study identified 62% of depression, anxiety and alcohol abuse in pulmonary tuberculosis patients. Among these psychiatric disorders, 40 patients are with depressive disorders, 8 patients with Panic disorder, 6 patients with generalized anxiety disorder and 18 patients with dual diagnosis. Among depressive disorders, 20 patients are with mild depression, 14 with moderate depression and 6 with severe depression. The prevalence of these psychiatric disorders in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis is significantly high. Depression is the commonest among them.

Keywords: Depression, anxiety, alcohol abuse, pulmonary tuberculosis.

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Introduction

In medically ill patients psychiatric disorders occur frequently, depression, anxiety, alcohol abuse, delirium, dementia, etc. are common [1,2]. These are more frequently seen in chronic medical illnesses like Pulmonary TB, Diabetes, HIV, and cancer. Reasons for the Psychiatric disorders could be reactions to stresses of medical illness and treatment or physiological consequence of illness [3].

Adam J. Trenton et al [4,5] studied comorbidity of TB and mental disorders and suggested diagnostic and treatment guidelines for TB comorbid disorders. Usually mood disorders lead to non-compliance to treatment in MDR TB. Psychiatric patients are more prone to TB infection as they are homeless or unstable housing and they may spend more time in heavily populated shelters where infection is common and are often untreated. Even

if TB is diagnosed, these people have poor compliance and exacerbating the illness spread.

The prevalence of depression, anxiety disorders and alcohol abuse in the world population is 4.5%, 4% and 1.4% respectively. Despite the availability of inexpensive therapy, tuberculosis is the leading cause of death. (Modules 1-4 RNTCP) [6] TB kills more adults than any other infectious illness. More than 1000 per day die of TB in our country, despite the presence of National Tuberculosis Programme since 1962.

The aim of present study is to determine the prevalence of depression, anxiety and alcohol abuse in pulmonary tuberculosis patients. TB is painful experience in biopsychosocial history of an individual.

The chronicity, disease burden, high risk of morbidity and mortality make TB dreadful disease with impact on the psyche of patients. Poverty, illiteracy, social stigma, result in isolation of victims. Against this backdrop, understanding of psycho-social, psycho-somatic implications is necessary. The interplay between these factors in etiology, course and outcome of the disease is key to furtherance of endless endeavour in fighting TB more effectively in coming future. The depression, anxiety, alcohol abuse in medical disorders is neglected area. The data about prevalence, incidence, and pathophysiology are less.

Very few studies are present and the present study is an attempt in that direction.

Materials and Methods

Study design: Hospital based cross sectional study.

Study subjects: 100 patients diagnosed as pulmonary tuberculosis using ATT drugs after 2 months of completion.

Sample technique: Simple random sampling.

Study setting: Department of TBCD (OPD), S.V.V.R.G.H, Tirupati.

Study period: A period of one year.

f) Study method: After taking informed and written consent from patients and their family members, the study subjects were interviewed along with the attendant. Data regarding socio demographic details were taken using semi-structured proforma.

Then MINI scale was applied for screening, then the diagnosis Depression, Anxiety and alcohol abuse by DSM IV TR and evaluated by Hamilton depression rating scale which is multiple item questionnaire for assessing severity of depression, AUDIT scale for severity of alcohol abuse were applied. Based on the data collected the results were analysed by SPSS 17 software.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Patients above 18-60 years of age.
2. Patients diagnosed as having pulmonary tuberculosis, by x-ray and/or sputum examination, after completion of 2 months using ATT.
3. Written Informed consent.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patient with pulmonary tuberculosis with extra pulmonary tuberculosis and other significant medical illness.
2. Patients who are known defaulters.

Scales:

1. Kuppaswamy's Socio-economic status scale.
2. The Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI).

3. The HDRS.
4. The Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT).
5. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM).

Ethics: Study protocol approved by Institutional Ethics Committee, Sri Venkateswara Medical College, and Tirupati.

Results

This study sample consists of 100 patients suffering from pulmonary tuberculosis after completion of 2 months of ATT drugs.

Age & Sex: In the present study majority of patients in age group of 41-50 years. There were 8(8%) patients in the age group of 18-20y.

Among them 7(7%) are males and 1(1%) is female. There were 16(16%) patients in the age group of 21-30y, among them 7(7%) are males and 9(9%) are females.

In the age group of 31-40y there were 21(21%) patients, among them 13(13%) males and 8(8%) females.

In the age group of 41-50y there were 29(29%) patients, among them 16(16%) were males and 13(13%) were females.

In the age group of 51-60y there were 26 patients, among them 15(15%) were males and 11(11%) were females. Most of the patients in the present study were males. There were 58(58%) males and 42(42%) females.

Religion: In the present study majority of the patients were Hindus. There were 76 Hindu patients (76%), 11 Muslim patients (11%) and 13 Christian patients (13%)

Residence: In the present study majority of patients were from Urban background. There were 36(36%) patients from urban areas, 30 (30%) patients from semi urban area and 34 (34%) are from rural background.

Educational status: In the present study majority of the patients were illiterates and have studied high school. There were 24 (24%) illiterates, 20 (20.0%) with primary education, 14 (14%) with secondary education, 26(26%) high school, 10(10%) completed PUC/diploma, 6(6%) with graduation or Post-graduation.

Occupational Status

In the present study majority of the patients were unemployed.

There were 34(34%) unemployed, 29(29%) unskilled workers, 19(19%) were semi-skilled workers, 10(10%) were skilled workers, 2(2%)

were shop owners and 3(3%) were semi-professional and 3(3%) were professional.

INCOME Status:

In the present study the patients with family income 15536-20714 were major group with 35(35%) of patients. There were 4 (4%) of patients with income of 2092-6213.

There were 22(22%) patients with monthly family income of 6214-10356, there were 10 (10%) patients with monthly income of 20715-41429 and 1(1%) with >41430 Rs.

Socio Economic Status: Socio economic status is measured by modified Kuppaswamy classification for socio economic factors. In the present study majority of the patients belonged to upper lower 43(43%). 10(10%) belong to lower class, 39(39%) belong to lower middle and 5(5%) belong to upper middle and 3(3%) patients belong to upper class.

Depression:

In the present study majority of patients have depressive disorder, out of them 20% (20) have mild depression, 14% (14) have moderate depression and 6 have severe depression.

Table 1: Depression frequency and percentage in total sample

		Frequency	Percent
Depression	Nil	60	60.0
	Mild Depression	20	20.0
	Moderate Depression	14	14.0
	Severe Depression	6	6.0
Anxiety Disorders	Nil	86	86.0
	Panic Disorder	8	8.0
	Generalized Anxiety disorder (GAD)	6	6.0
Alcohol Abuse	Nil	72	72.0
	Mild	12	12.0
	Moderate	9	9.0
	Severe	7	7.0

Anxiety disorders: Among anxiety disorders 8 (8%) had panic disorder and 6 (6%) had generalized anxiety disorder.

Alcohol abuse: Among alcohol use disorder 12(12%) had mild abuse, 9(9%) had moderate abuse and 7 (7%) had severe abuse.

Table 2: Association between sex and depression

			Depression				Total
			Nil	Mild depression	Moderate Depression	Severe Depression	
SEX	Male	Count	32	14	8	4	58
		% within SEX	55.2%	24.1%	13.8%	6.9%	100.0%
	Female	Count	28	6	6	2	42
		% within SEX	66.7%	14.3%	14.3%	4.8%	100.0%
Total		Count	60	20	14	6	100
		% within SEX	60.0%	20.0%	14.0%	6.0%	100.0%

Pearson Chi-Square =1.908; p=0.592

Association between sex and depression:

Males showed more prevalence of depression than females in the present study. There were 58 males, among them 14(24.1%) have mild and have 8(13.8%) moderate and 4 (6.9%) have severe

depression. Among 42 females, 6 (14.3 %) have mild, 6(14.3 %) have moderate and 2 (4.8%) have severe depression.

The p value of 0.592 in the group statistics is not significant.

Table 3: Association between Residence and Depression

			Depression				Total
			Nil	Mild Depression	Moderate Depression	Severe Depression	
Residence	Urban	Count	24	6	4	2	36
		% within Residence	66.7%	16.7%	11.1%	5.6%	100.0%
	Semiurban	Count	14	8	6	2	30
		% within Residence	46.7%	26.7%	20.0%	6.7%	100.0%
	Rural	Count	22	6	4	2	34
		% within Residence	64.7%	17.6%	11.8%	5.9%	100.0%
Total		Count	60	20	14	6	100
		% within Residence	60.0%	20.0%	14.0%	6.0%	100.0%

Pearson Chi-Square=3.384; p=0.759

In the present study prevalence of depression was more among patients belonging to semi-urban background. There were 36 patients from urban background with 6 (16.7%) having mild, 4 having (11.1%) moderate and 2 having (5.6%) severe depression. 30 patients from semi urban

background 8 (26.7%) with mild, 6 (20.0%) with moderate and 2 (6.7%) with severe depression. 34 patients from rural background among whom 6 (17.6%) have mild, 4 have (11.8%) moderate and 2 have (5.9%) severe depression. The p value of 0.759 in overall group statistics is not significant.

Table 4: Association between sex and alcohol abuse

			Alcohol Abuse				Total
			Nil	Mild	Moderate	Severe	
SEX	Male	Count	35	8	8	7	58
		% within Sex	60.3%	13.8%	13.8%	12.1%	100.0%
	Female	Count	37	4	1	0	42
		% within Sex	88.1%	9.5%	2.4%	0.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	72	12	9	7	100
		% within Sex	72.0%	12.0%	9.0%	7.0%	100.0%

Pearson Chi-Square=11.570; p=0.009

In the present study prevalence of alcohol is more in males. Among 58 males 8(13.8%) have mild severity, 8(13.8%) have moderate severity and 7(12.1%) have severe severity of alcohol abuse. In 42 females 4 (9.5%) have mild and 1(2.4%) has moderate alcohol abuse value of 0.009 among group statistics is significant.

Discussion

The present study shows prevalence of depression, anxiety and alcohol abuse in patients suffering from pulmonary tuberculosis taking anti tubercular drugs after completion of 2 months. In this study alcohol is taken, as it is more prevalent in the study setting.

In the present study majority of patients in age group of 41-50 years. There were 8(8%) patients in the age group of 18-20 years. Among them 7(7%) are males and 1(1%) is female. There were 16(16%) patients in the age group of 21-30y, among them 7 (7%) are males and 9(9%) are females. In the age group of 31-40yr there were 21(21%) patients, among them 13(13%) males and 8(8%) females. In the age group of 41-50y there were 29(29%) patients, among them 16(16%) were males and 13(13%) were females. In the age group of 51-60y there were 26 patients, among them

15(15%) were males and 11(11%) were females. In this study out of a sample of 100, 58 (58%) were males while 42 (42%) were females. Most of the patients are Hindus 76 patients (76%), Muslims 11 patients (11%) and Christians 13 patients (13%). 36% (36) patients belonged to an urban background while, 30% (30) patients belonged to semi urban area and 34% (34) belonged to rural background. 24 (24%) were illiterates, 20 (20.0%) with primary education, 14 (14%) who studied up to middle school, 26 (26.0%) with high school education, 10(10.0%) completed intermediate/ diploma, 6(6.0%) with graduation. Majority of patients have studied high school. Most of the patients are unemployed 34(34.0%), 29(29.0%) were unskilled workers, 19(19.0%) were semi-skilled workers, 10(10.0%) were skilled workers, 2(2.0%) were shop owners, and 3(3.0%) were semi-professionals and 3(3.0%) were professionals. 10 (10%) patients belong to lower socio economic class, 43 (43%) patients belong to upper lower class, 39 (39%) belong lower middle class, 5(5%) belong to upper middle class and 3(3%) belong to upper socio economic status. Out of the 64 (64%) patients with depression, anxiety and alcohol abuse disorders, 18 qualified for more than one diagnosis, 40 patients are diagnosed to have depressive illness, 8 have

panic disorder, 6 patients have GAD, 28 patients has alcohol abuse and 36 patients are completely free from depression, anxiety and abuse.

In the present study 64 (64%) patients, with pulmonary tuberculosis using anti tubercular drugs have depression, anxiety and alcohol abuse disorders. Among them depressive disorders are more 40 patients (62.5%), followed by alcohol abuse disorder 28 patients (43.75%). There are 14 patients only with anxiety disorders. The above result are comparable with Indian studies done by Purohit et al [7] in an incidence study of depression in hospitalized pulmonary Tuberculosis patients using self-rating depression scale of Zung in 96 patients, found that 54.17% had depression, Gupta et al [8] studied relation between life events, physical illness and psychiatric morbidity. 60 patients of pulmonary tuberculosis were selected through a specified procedure from T.B. hospital Bikaner. P.S.E scale was applied on all patients and found that 41.6% had depression, Maghnani et al [9] studied depression in hospitalized pulmonary tuberculosis patients and role of anti-depressants, using HAM-D and clinical global rating scale among 110 patients, and depression was found in 53.6%, Swarna latha Panchal [10] studied the prevalence of depression Using Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) in 600 tuberculosis patients and observed depression in 82% of the females. In this study the prevalence of anxiety disorders in patients suffering from pulmonary tuberculosis is not statistically significant with the sex and It is comparable with earlier studies done by John Mathai et al [11], Silverstone [12] and not comparable with studies by Amreen et al [13] in Pakistan, where prevalence of anxiety was also significantly higher in female patients, because of bio-psycho social stressors.

Conclusion

The majority is depressive disorders followed by alcohol abuse disorders. The prevalence of these psychiatric disorders in patients with pulmonary tuberculosis is significantly high. Depression is the commonest among them.

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